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Research

Article

**MINI-CHOLECYSTECTOMY, EXPERIENCE OF 200 CASES
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Cheema³, Dr Sobia Zafar⁴, Dr Sufyan Zia⁵, Dr Ahsan Iqbal⁶**¹⁻⁶ District Head Quarter Teaching Hospital Gujranwala**Abstract:**

The field of medical surgery was revolutionized by the introduction of laparoscopy. In 1985, Prof Dr. Med Erich Möhe of Böblingen, Germany became the first ever doctor to perform the first ever laparoscopic cholecystectomy [1]. The procedure grew fundamentally over the period of time and especially in the last few decades it has achieved a very high status in the management of cholelithiasis. However, many third world countries still couldn't replace open cholecystectomy with laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Mini-cholecystectomy is an easier, feasible and secure choice with less operation and surgery time, lesser complications, good prognosis and lesser postoperative care and hospital stay. It can be a choice and better option for those medical service facilities where laparoscopic facilities are not available

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INTRODUCTION:

The field of medical surgery was revolutionized by the introduction of laparoscopy. In 1985, Prof Dr. Med Erich Mühe of Böblingen, Germany became the first ever doctor to perform the first ever laparoscopic cholecystectomy [1]. The procedure grew fundamentally over the period of time and especially in the last few decades it has achieved a very high status in the management of cholelithiasis. However, many third world countries still couldn't replace open cholecystectomy with laparoscopic cholecystectomy. In order to reduce the pain, stay in hospital and the scar of the procedure, a procedure called mini-cholecystectomy was introduced in 1970s which not only reduced the morbidity but also reduced the operative pain involved in it[2].

Where the standard cholecystectomy required 7-10cm incision [3], the mini-cholecystectomy requires only 3-5 cm with either muscle splitting or retracting. The only drawback to this procedure is that it requires significant amount of training and surgical experience with good assistance.

The introduction of laparoscopic cholecystectomy was revolutionary in the management of gall bladder diseases but some surgeons prefer mini-cholecystectomy over laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The current study was carried out to examine cholecystectomy through 5 cm mini-laparotomy incision. No expensive instrument like laparoscope was required for this study.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

From Jan 2011 to Dec 2015, a total of 200 patients of cholelithiasis were included in this study irrespective of their gender and age at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. Factors like pain, complications and stay in hospital was to be noted after the conduction of mini-cholecystectomy.

A detailed history and careful medical examination of the patients were done prior to operation. All the tests necessary to know normal functioning of respiratory and cardio-vascular system were performed on all the patients. To assess the condition of liver and intra & extra biliary passages, Ultrasonography was performed. Keeping in view the results of the tests, patients with abnormal liver functioning & dilated CBD were not included in the study because of the limited exposure of the region in the study.

All patients were operated under general anesthesia along with muscle relaxants. A transverse incision of 5 cm was performed in the right sub costal region directly over the gall bladder. A sharp dissection was used to cut the skin, subcutaneous fat and anterior rectus sheaths. This was followed by muscle splitting in elderly and muscle division in younger patients. Followed by the opening of peritoneum the juncture of cystic duct with CBD was pointed out. Distended gall bladder was aspirated first because empty gall bladder is relatively easier to dissect. Ligation of artery and cystic duct was done with vicryl no 1 suture. 2/0 or 3/0 Prolinesubcuticular stitch was used to close the abdominal wall in layers & skin. Nasogastric tubes were not used on any patients while sub hepatic suction was used in 15 patients. Patients were given permission to consume oral liquids and light diet after 24 hours of operation.

RESULTS:

Mini-cholecystectomy was possible in almost 95% of the cases. Incision had to be extended in the rest of the 5% (10cases) cases. 2.5% of the cases had acute cholecystitis while the other 2.5% of the cases had mucocoelel of gall bladder. The mean operating time was almost 50mins with an average blood loss of 100ml. patients on average had to stay for 2 days at the hospital.

Table 1: Age & Sex Distribution of Patients

Age Group (years)	Number of Patients
35-50	80
51-55	70
56-60	50
SEX	
Male	120
Female	80

Table 2: Results of Procedure

Parameters	Results
Average Operation time	50 min
Post Operation Complications	10 cases (5%)
Delayed return of Bowl habits	4 cases (2%)
Mean hospital stay	2 days
Intra-abdominal drain	20 cases (10%)
Work disability	6-8 days
Difficulties at operation	12 cases incision needed to be extended

Table 3: Complications of Mini-cholecystectomy

Complication	Number of cases
Wound Infection	4 (2%)
Sub hepatic collection	3 (1.5%)
Ileus	3 (1.5%)
Wound dehiscence	Nil
Pancreatitis	Nil
Urological Infection	Nil
Pulmonary complications	Nil
Total	10 (5%)

Table 4: Patients in whom incision had to be extended

Patient no.	Age (years)	Pathology	Anatomical findings
1	45	Acute Cholecystitis	Normal
2	47	Acute Cholecystitis	Normal
3	56	Acute Cholecystitis	Normal
4	52	Acute Cholecystitis	Normal
5	50	Acute Cholecystitis	Normal
6	60	Mucocele gall bladder	Normal
7	55	Chcholecystitis	Low insertion of cystic duct
8	46	Chcholecystitis	Low insertion of cystic duct
9	49	Chcholecystitis	Double cystic artery
10	48	Chcholecystitis	Double cystic artery

CONCLUSION:

Mini-cholecystectomy is an easier, feasible and secure choice with less operation and surgery time, lesser complications, good prognosis and lesser postoperative care and hospital stay. It can be a choice and better option for those medical service facilities where laparoscopic facilities are not available.

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